

FigS3. Data analysis on upshift data.

Fraction of cells displaying nuclear localization over time. Nuclear localization is defined by cells which nuclear fluorescence intensity exceeds the mean nuclear intensity plus standard deviation of the mean nuclear intensity at timepoint zero. (Panel A). The coefficient of variation per experiment over time per experiment (Panel B)